

Pavement Crack Detection and Solution with Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract:

Detecting and repairing pavement cracks is essential to ensure road safety and longevity. Traditional inspection and maintenance methods are time-consuming, expensive and often inaccurate. In recent years, there has been a growing trend to use artificial intelligence (AI) to automate the process of pavement crack detection and repair. The article focuses on using AI techniques to detect pavement cracks and provide solutions to repair them. The proposed solution is based on using deep learning algorithms to analyze high-resolution images of the road surface. Photos are taken with a vehicle camera or a drone. The deep learning algorithm is trained using a large data set of tagged sidewalk crack images. Once

trained, the algorithm can accurately detect and classify the type of cracks on the pavement surface, including longitudinal, transverse, block and crocodile cracks. The algorithm can also determine the severity of each crack and help prioritize repairs. When cracks are detected, the AI system can make recommendations for repair solutions. This includes identifying the appropriate caulk or filler material to use depending on the type and severity of the crack. The AI system can also recommend the most efficient and cost-effective repair method, such as B. Crack sealing, crack filling or deep repair. Overall, using AI to detect and repair cracks in sidewalks offers a more accurate, efficient, and cost-effective solution to keep roads safe and sustainable. By automating the inspection and repair process, this technology can help prevent accidents, reduce maintenance costs, and improve overall road safety.

Introduction

Pavement cracks are a common problem that can lead to safety hazards and increase maintenance costs. Traditional pavement crack detection and repair methods can be time and money consuming. However, with advances in artificial intelligence (AI), it is now possible to detect and treat pavement cracks with greater accuracy and efficiency. AI technology can provide a quick and accurate solution to detect cracks in the pavement by analyzing images captured by vehicle-mounted cameras or drones. The system can detect cracks of varying sizes and severity, allowing maintenance teams to prioritize repairs based on immediate need. Once cracks are identified, AI algorithms can recommend the best repair method based on the type and severity of damage. This can help reduce the time and materials needed for repairs, as well as minimize disruption to traffic flow and efficient (Hoang, & Nguyen, 2018).

Objectives

Develop an AI-Based Crack Detection System: The primary objective is to design and develop an automatic crack detection system using AI techniques. This involves training a machine learning model, such as a convolutional neural network (CNN), to accurately detect and classify pavement cracks in images.

Improve crack detection accuracy: Improve crack detection accuracy by exploring advanced AI algorithms and techniques. This includes investigating state-of-the-art object detection methods such as Faster R-CNN, SSD, or YOLO and evaluating their performance in detecting pavement cracks.

Evaluate the effectiveness of the crack detection system: Conduct a thorough evaluation of the developed crack detection system to evaluate its effectiveness. This involves measuring metrics such as precision, recall, F1 score and precision to determine the reliability of the system in detecting different types and severities of cracks.

Propose solutions for pavement repair and maintenance: Based on cracks detected, recommend appropriate repair and maintenance techniques. This objective involves developing algorithms or decision-making frameworks that consider the severity, location and other characteristics of cracks to effectively manage the repair and maintenance process.

Application

Efficient crack detection: AI-based crack detection systems can automate the process of identifying and classifying pavement cracks in images or video footage. This application saves time and labor compared to manual inspection methods. This allows quick and accurate detection of cracks, enabling early intervention and timely maintenance.

The improved maintenance planning: Using AI algorithms, the severity and extent of pavement cracks can be assessed more accurately. This information can be used to prioritize maintenance and repair activities based on the urgency and impact of cracks. As a result, limited resources can be effectively allocated to areas requiring immediate attention to improve the overall maintenance plan.

Proactive Infrastructure Management: AI-based crack detection systems enable proactive infrastructure management. By continuously monitoring the condition of the pavement, the system can detect and alert authorities to the appearance of new cracks.

Pavement Crack Problem Statement

A pavement crack statement refers to a crack that occurs on paved surfaces, such as roads, parking lots, and sidewalks. These cracks appear due to a variety of factors, including weather conditions, heavy traffic, and age-related wear and tear, among others. Cracks can worsen over time and lead to further damage to the pavement, which can affect the structural integrity of the pavement and the safety of road

users. This issue statement highlights the need for effective pavement repair and maintenance strategies to address crack problems and ensure the durability and safety of paved surfaces (Ahmadi, Khalesi, & Bagheri, 2018).

Companion of Supervised Classification Techniques of Vision Based

As an AI language model, I cannot make a comparison without knowing the specific supervised classification techniques used for vision-based pavement crack detection. However, typical supervised classification techniques involve training a machine learning model with labeled data, which can then be used to classify new data based on characteristics. its point. The accuracy and performance of the classifier depends on various factors, such as the quality of the labeled data, the complexity of the model, and the algorithm chosen. Some of the supervised classification techniques commonly used in pavement crack detection include support vector machines (SVMs), random forests (RFs), and convolutional neural networks (CNNs). Each technique has strengths and weaknesses in terms of accuracy, efficiency, and generalizability, and the choice of technique may depend on specific requirements and application context (Peng, Fu, & Jiang, 2016).

1. Pavement Assessment and Crack Rating Computer vision-based crack detection approach
2. Image processing techniques for crack detection

3. Future mining for assessment pavement price
4. Evaluation of road cracks at network level
5. Comparison of techniques
6. Detailed symbols
 - a. The pavement crack index is a method used to measure the severity and extent of cracks in the pavement.
 - b. The scoring system is usually based on the size, depth, distance and type of cracks found in the pavement.
 - c. Different regions may use different rating systems to assess road cracks based on site characteristics such as weather conditions, traffic loads, and materials.
 - d. The purpose of crack assessment is to prioritize maintenance and repair activities to prevent the formation of potholes, marks and other unsafety hazards.
 - e. Regular maintenance and repair of pavement cracks can significantly improve road safety and durability (FDOT Office, 2022).
 - f. The crack assessment system helps transit agencies determine an appropriate maintenance and repair strategy based on the severity and location of the crack. These strategies may include sealing or filling cracks, resurfacing or re-paving the pavement, or rebuilding the whole thing (FDOT Office, 2022).

Figure 1. Total Lane Miles Rated
Source: FHART, 2017

Figure 2. Computer Vision-Based Check PETITIZ on Approaches
 Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 3. Step 1 - Image Processing Morph Link-c by (USF)
 Source: Hoang, Nguyen, & Bui, 2018

Figure 4. Step 2 - Future Selection
 Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 5. Classification
 Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 6. Step 3 - Classification
Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 7. Classification
Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

	Class I B	Class II	Class III	Classification
Crack type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single • Branch (moderate) • Block 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single • Branch (severe) • Block • Alligator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single • Branch (severe) • Block • Alligator 	Qualitative
Crack width	$\leq 1/8"$ or $\leq 3.18\text{mm}$ 	$> 1/8"$ TO $\leq 1/4"$ or $> 3.18\text{mm}$ TO $\leq 6.35\text{mm}$ 	$> 1/4"$ or $> 6.35\text{mm}$ 	Quantitative

Figure 8. Crack Rating – AASHTO Approach
Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 9. Raw Image
 Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 10. CrackView –ASTM Approach
 Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 11. Crack View
 Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 12. Crack Rating for Large Road Network
 Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 13. GPRS Tracking
 Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 14. Network-Leveling Picture Rating for San Antonio TX Using Crack View
Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Crack Statistics: Principal Road

- Length: 36 mi
- # images: 25,271
- # cracks: 995,271
- Cracks/mi: 27,646

	Avg	Stdv	10 Quant	90 Quant
Area (mm ²)	860.00	426.26	34.00	1424.00
Length (mm)	153.24	423.39	10.00	326.00
Width (mm)	4.20	5.86	2.32	6.30
Orientation (deg)	3.19	75.98	-86.63	86.653

Figure 15. Crack Station Principal: Principal Road

Chapter 3: Classification Method Pavement Detection

Pavement condition information is an important component of a pavement management system. Labeling and quantifying the type, severity and extent of surface cracking is a difficult area to weigh asphalt pavements. This article presents a general review of different background and

image processing methods for the interpretation of asphalt surfaces (Kailiang, 2012). The main body of this study presents the complete combination of the most advanced image processing technology based on the interpretation of (Wang, 2016).

Asphalt pavement-related cracks. An attempt is made to examine existing methods from different perspectives accompanied by an in-

depth three-step comparison of incident detection, classification and quantification methods to facilitate studies. next. This article presents an overview of pavement inspection

systems developed to date. In addition, emerging and developing technologies considered for automating processes are also discussed (Wang, 2016).

Figure 16. Classification Methods

Source: Tan et al., 2022

Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

The ANN is network of simple processing unit called neurons which are connected using of weights and biases.

Figure 17. Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

Source: Wang, 2016

K-Neares Neighbors (KNN)

The k-nearest neighbor algorithm, also known as KNN or k-NN, is a non-parametric supervised classification algorithm that uses close distance to perform classification or prediction on a one-point cluster. of individual data (Yang, & Geng, 2018).

Figure 18. K-Neares Neighbors (KNN)

Source: Maheshwari, 2018

A decision tree is a non-parametric supervised learning algorithm that is used for both classification and regression tasks. It has a hierarchical tree structure, consisting of a root node, branches, inner nodes, and leaf nodes (Wang, & Pyle, 2019).

Adaptive Neuro fuzzy inference system (ANFIS)

The ANFIS is a combination of neural network and fuzzy system. The ANFIS structure has five main layers between input and output (Sulistyaningrum et al., 2020). The inputs are converted to fuzzy inputs using membership functions through the first layer, which is called blur (Sulistyaningrum et al., 2020).

Figure 19. ANFIS
Source: Piscopo, 2018

Concerns in Classifier Training Pavement

Limited data availability: Pavement classification requires large amounts of data, including surface condition data, traffic load data, and pavement texture data. However, data availability may be limited, especially in developing countries, which may affect the accuracy of the classifier (Zhou et al., 2022).

Change in pavement condition: Road surface condition varies widely due to factors such as weather conditions, traffic volume, and maintenance practices. This variation could make it difficult to develop precise classifiers capable of classifying all types of pavement conditions. **Selection of appropriate properties:** The selection of appropriate properties is crucial for effective pavement classification. The selection of features can affect the accuracy of

the classifier, and the selection process can be complex and require specialized knowledge.

Limited understanding of pavement behavior: There is still limited understanding of pavement behavior and performance, especially under different conditions. This can affect the accuracy of the classifier, as the model may not accurately predict pavement behavior under new conditions.

Model Complexity: The complexity of a classification model can affect its accuracy and performance. Models that are more complex can capture the complexity of pavement behavior, but they can also be more prone to overfitting.

Incorrect data labeling: Incorrect data labeling can lead to the development of less efficient classifiers. Data labeling requires expert knowledge, and labeling errors can affect the accuracy of the classifier.

On addressing these concerns requires careful consideration of the dataset, model, and training process. Regular testing and validation can help ensure that the classifier is efficient and unbiased. Furthermore, the selection of the right features and careful data labeling are critical to developing an effective classifier. Using expert knowledge and developing a better understanding of pavement behavior can also improve the accuracy of pavement classification (Zhou et al., 2022).

Taring Parameter

Training data: The selection and preparation of training data is critical to developing an accurate model of pavement deterioration. The data should be representative of pavement condition and include information on pavement life, traffic loads, climate, and maintenance history.

Feature selection: The selection of the right features is critical to model accuracy. The characteristics must be appropriate for

pavement deterioration, and their selection may require specialized knowledge.

Model selection: Model selection can affect the accuracy and complexity of pavement damage modeling. Commonly used models for pavement degradation include Markov chain models, artificial neural networks, and regression models.

Learning algorithm: The learning algorithm is used to optimize the model's parameters to best fit the training data. Common training algorithms include gradient descent, random gradient descent, and backpropagation (Wang, et al., 2019).

Imbalanced Data

In Unbalanced, data can be a common problem in pavement data analysis, where some types of pavement failure may be much less common than others can. This can lead to erroneous and inaccurate analysis results.

Figure 20. Mbalanced Data

Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016; Majidifard, Adu-Gyamfi, & Buttlar, 2020

In there are several approaches to dealing with unbalanced data in pavement analysis, including:

Oversampling: Oversampling involves increasing the number of samples in the minority class for weighing, by class distribution. This can be done by duplicating existing samples or by generating composite samples using techniques such as SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique).

Down sampling: Down sampling involves reducing the number of samples in the majority class to balance the distribution of the class. This can be done by randomly dropping samples or using more advanced techniques like to make association or edited nearest neighbor.

Cost-sensitive learning: Cost-sensitive learning involves assigning different costs to misclassify each class. This can help the algorithm focus more on the minority group (Majidifard, Adu-Gyamfi, & Buttlar, 2020).

Data Preparation Number of Crack

Preparing data for pavement crack detection involves several steps, including: Data collection:

Collecting images and videos of the pavement using cameras or drones.

Data Caption: Label the image with the location and type of pavement crack. This can be done manually or using automated tools.

Data cleaning: Remove all poor quality or irrelevant images that may not be suitable for analysis.

Data enhancement: Create new images using techniques like rotation, scaling, and flipping.

This can help increase the size of the dataset and improve the generalizability of the model.

Feature Extraction: Extracting related features from an image can help distinguish between crack types. different. This may include techniques such as edge detection and texture analysis.

Normalize data: Scale the data to a common range to ensure the model can handle variations in the input data.

Data Separation: Split the data into training, validation and test sets. The training set is used to train the model, the validation set is used to tune the model's hyper parameters, and the test set is used to evaluate the final model's performance.

Figure 21. Data Piparation Number of Crack

Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Classification of Pavement Data Has Several Applications Including

- **Assess pavement condition:** Classification of pavement data can be used to assess overall pavement condition. This can help

identify areas that need maintenance or repair and prioritize maintenance activities based on the severity of the damage.

- **Predictive maintenance:** Classification of pavement data can be used to predict future pavement conditions. This can help plan

maintenance activities in advance and reduce the need for reactive maintenance (Dheyaaldin, 2020).

- **Property Management:** Classifying sidewalk data can be used to more effectively manage sidewalk assets. This includes identifying areas that need maintenance or replacement and monitoring the effectiveness of maintenance activities over time.

- **Cost Estimation:** The pavement data classification can be used to estimate the cost of maintenance activities. This can help to allocate resources more efficiently and effectively.

- **Performance analysis:** Pavement data classification can be used to analyze the performance of different pavement types and construction techniques. This can help identify best practices and improve new pavement designs (Dheyaaldin, 2020).

Figure 22. Classification of Pavement Data Has Several Applications, Including

Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Comparison of Performance and Computation Time

In machine learning, the performance and computation time of different models can be compared using different metrics. Some common metrics to compare performance include accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 scores. Computation time can be measured using a variety of tools, such as the time it takes to train the model or the time it takes to make predictions on new data.

When comparing performance and computation time, there is often a trade-off between the two. For example, models that are more complex can achieve higher accuracy but may require longer computation time. On the other hand, simpler models can compute faster but may sacrifice some accuracy (Sadati, et al., 2021).

Membership Functions in the Adaptive Fuzzy Neural Inference System (ANFIS)

Classifier play an important role in determining the accuracy of the model output. Member functions are used to map input data to fuzzy sets, which are then used to determine the output of the classifier.

In ANFIS, membership functions are usually represented using either a Gaussian distribution or a sigmoid function. Gaussian membership functions are often used for numeric or continuous input variables, while sigmoid membership functions are used for binary or categorical input variables.

The shape of the member function can also be customized according to the nature of the input data. For example, if the input data is skewed towards one end of the distribution, a triangular or trapezoidal membership function can be used to better capture the input data.

The ANFIS classifier uses associative learning that combines the strengths of fuzzy logic and

neural networks. During the training phase, ANFIS models use a combination of back-propagation and least squares regression to optimize the parameters of the membership

functions. This allows the classifier to adapt to changes in the input data and improve its accuracy over time.

Figure 23. Comparison of Performance and Computation Time

Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 24. ANFIS

Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Summary

In summary, pavement condition classification is an important task in the field of transportation engineering. Road surface conditions can have a significant impact on vehicle safety, traffic volume and operating costs. Machine learning techniques, such as the ANFIS classifier, have been applied to classify pavement conditions with promising results.

The one of the major challenges in pavement condition classification is dealing with unbalanced data. This problem can be solved by various techniques, such as data enhancement and oversampling.

In another important aspect of pavement condition classification is the selection of appropriate characteristics. Features that closely correlate with pavement condition, such as the

number and type of cracks, can significantly improve classifier accuracy.

Membership functions play an important role in ANFIS classifiers, allowing them to map input data to fuzzy sets and produce correct outputs. The appearance and parameters of member functions can be customized to meet specific application and input data needs (Sadati, et al., 2021).

In summary, machine learning techniques such as the ANFIS classifier have the potential to significantly improve the accuracy and efficiency of pavement condition classification. By addressing the challenges associated with feature selection and unbalanced data, and customizing membership functions, the ANFIS classifier can be optimized for a wide range of applications in the engineering field. transportation engineering (Sadati, et al., 2021).

Figure 25. ANFIS

Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Figure 26. Future Pavement Conditions

Source: Piscopo, 2018

On deep learning has become an increasingly popular technique for pavement evaluation due to its ability to automatically extract high-level features from raw input data. With deep learning, pavement assessment can be done more accurately, efficiently and automatically (Sadati, et al., 2021).

In one of the main advantages of deep learning for pavement assessment is its ability to learn

from large amounts of data. This allows deep learning models to capture complex relationships between input variables and produce highly accurate outputs. Deep learning models can also be customized to meet specific needs, such as identifying specific types of pavement deterioration or predicting future pavement conditions.

Figure 27. Sample CNN Results
Source: Mokhtari, Wu, & Yun, 2016

Crack Type Classification

In this section, horizontal cracks and cubic cracks are two common types of cracks that are reviewed and analyzed using several classification models such as decision trees, support vector machines (SVMs), nearest neighbors, etc (Cubero-Fernandez, et al., 2017).

To do this, it is necessary to first define the features and classes of the model's predictors, including some main features and some minor

features. Before describing these features, we will need to define the density matrix. To calculate the density matrix, first,

To the final binary crack image of is segmented into a 10×10 segment.

Then the density of each segment is calculated (equation 8).

Density of each segment = Number of cracked pixels in each segment (Liang, & Sun, 2012).

Main features:

$$F1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M (\sum_{j=1}^N DensityMatrix_{i,j})}{M}$$

$$F2 = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (\sum_{i=1}^M DensityMatrix_{i,j})}{N}$$

$$F3 = \frac{1}{M-1} \sum_{i=1}^M (DensityMatrix_{i,j} - F1)^2$$

$$F4 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{j=1}^N (DensityMatrix_{i,j} - F2)^2$$

S1= Set of row index which includes crack pixels

S1= Set of column index which includes crack pixels

$$F5 = \frac{\text{Max}(S1) - \text{Min}(S1)}{\text{Total number of rows}}$$

$$F6 = \frac{\text{Number of rows which includes crack pixels}}{\text{Total number of rows}}$$

$$F7 = \frac{\text{Max}(S2) - \text{Min}(S2)}{\text{Total number of columns}}$$

$$F8 = \frac{\text{Number of columns which includes crack pixels}}{\text{Total number of columns}}$$

(1) (Liang, & Sun, 2012)

The features which are used in classification model are defined as follows:

Additional features:

$$F9 = \frac{\text{Horizontal Average (Final binary image)}}{\text{Vertical Average (Final binary image)}}$$

$$F10 = \frac{\text{Horizontal STD (Final binary image)}}{\text{Vertical STD (Final binary image)}}$$

$$F11 = \frac{\text{Horizontal CV (Final binary image)}}{\text{Vertical CV (Final binary image)}}$$

$$F12 = \frac{\text{Horizontal Average (Density matrix)}}{\text{Vertical Average (Density matrix)}}$$

$$F13 = \frac{F1}{F2}, F14 = \frac{F1}{F3}, F15 = \frac{F2}{F4}, F16 = \frac{F3}{F4}$$

$$F17 = \frac{F5}{F6}, F18 = \frac{F5}{F7}, F19 = \frac{F7}{F8}, F20 = \frac{F6}{F8}$$

$$F21 = F5 \times F6, F22 = F7 \times F8$$

(2) (Kapela, et al., 2015)

Methodology

In Additional information is provided to better understand the architecture discussed. The convolution layer (Conv) plays a key role in CNN. During data transfer, sparse parameter interaction and sharing was achieved, which reduced the number of parameters in the CNN model and enabled the extraction of useful feature information. Mathematically, equation

(3) represents the convolution operation of the convolutional layer:^[25]

$$Conv(x)_{i,j} = \sum_m \sum_n X_{i-m, j-n} K_{m,n} \quad (3)$$

(Kapela, et al., 2015)

where X is a two-dimensional input matrix; K is convolution; and m and n are the row and column values of the convolution kernel. In expanded form, equation (3) is rewritten by

considering two different stride values, i.e. equals 1 and 2 (equations (4) and (5) respectively) (Song, et al., 2017).

Figure 28. Parallel Residual Convolutional Neural Network for Crack Detection: (a) the Architecture of Parallel ResNet; (b) Exploded View

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b & c & d \\ e & f & g & h \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} i & j \\ k & l \end{bmatrix} = [ai + bj + ek + fl \quad bi + cj + fk + gl \quad ci + dj + fk + hl]$$

(4) (Yang, et al., 2022)

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b & c & d \\ e & f & g & h \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} i & j \\ k & l \end{bmatrix} = [ai + bj + ek + fl \quad ci + dj + fk + hl]$$

(5) (Yang, et al., 2022)

where $\begin{bmatrix} a & b & c & d \\ e & f & g & h \end{bmatrix}$ is the input two-dimensional tensor; and $\begin{bmatrix} i & j \\ k & l \end{bmatrix}$ is a 2×2 convolutional kernel tensor. (6)

Figure 29. Parallel ResNet Module:
(a) Standard Convolutional Layer; (b) Skip Connected Convolutional Layer

Figure 29 Parallel Res Net module: (a) standard convolutional layer; (b) skip connected convolutional layer; (c) Parallel Res Net module of 3 Res Nets.

Figure 29a, which represents two standard convolutional layers. The related function is defined by Equation (7):

$$H(x) = F(x) \quad (7) \text{ (Yang, et al., 2022)}$$

In Figure 29b, which shows a residual module skipping two convolutional layers ($L = 2$). The mathematical expression is described by Equation (5):

$$H(x) = F(x) + x \quad (8) \text{ (Yang, et al., 2022)}$$

In Figure 29c, a Parallel ResNet module with three branches in parallel. The structure of each branch in the parallel module is the same. For example, the first parallel branch is composed of a residual block skipping two convolutional layers (Conv_A_1 and Conv_B_1), and a convolutional layer (Conv_1) with a stride of 2. Finally, through the add operation, the module outputs $N(x)$ (Song, et al., 2017).

The Parallel ResNet module function is described by the following Equations (6)-(10)

$$H_i(x) = x^l + \sum_{k=1}^L F_i(x^k)$$

$$F_i(x^k) = f(C_0^k, C_1^k, \dots, C_c^k)$$

$$C_m^k = \sum_{n \in x_m} x_i^{k-1} * w_{nm}^l + b_m^l$$

$$L_i(x) = H_i(x) \otimes W_i + t_i$$

$$N(x) = \sum^n L_i(x) \quad (10)$$

Accuracy Test

The performance of the line damage classifier using deep learning was determined by the accuracy of the and Io U object classifier (intersection on Union). The equation for the accuracy of the classification is shown in (11) (CPTP, 2009).

$$\text{Accuracy} = (\text{TP} + \text{TN}) / (\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}) \quad (11)$$

where TP (True Positive) is the correctly classified object type, TN (true negative) is another category on the correctly classified subject, FP (false positive) is a type of subject, that is not correctly classified, while FN (false negative) is another type of object that is not , correctly classifies the Union upper bounding box (Io U) Io U calculates the area of intersection between the object prediction box and the ground truth box and divides by the union area of they. The Io U formula is specified in (12) (Feng, et al., 2020).

$$\text{IoU} = \text{Oberlap area} / \text{Bond area} \quad (12)$$

PQC Cracks

In PQC (Road Quality Concrete) cracks are cracks that appear in the concrete pavement, which can lead to significant deterioration in pavement performance and service life. These cracks can occur due to many factors, including environmental factors such as changes in temperature and humidity, as well as traffic loads and pavement aging (Sharma, 2019).

There are several types of PQC cracks, including horizontal cracks perpendicular to the roadway direction, longitudinal cracks parallel to the roadway direction, and diagonal cracks. Each type of crack can indicate different potential problems with the pavement, such as poor pavement design or construction, insufficient pavement thickness, or inadequate joint spacing.

In PQC cracks can be assessed using a variety of techniques including visual inspection, crack mapping, and non-destructive testing. Once cracks are identified, appropriate repair techniques can be implemented to prevent further deterioration of the pavement. These techniques may include sealing cracks, which involves filling the cracks with sealing material to prevent water and debris from escaping, or crack sealing, which involves filling the cracks. with flexible materials can adapt to the movement of the road (Sharma, 2019).

The Preventive maintenance techniques, such as regular crack sealing and joint maintenance, can also help prolong pavement life and prevent more serious types of damage from occurring. By identifying and repairing PQC cracks promptly, pavement owners can ensure that their pavement remains in good condition and continues to provide a safe, smooth driving surface for years to come (Ellsi, Langdale, & Cook, 2002).

The structural cracks classified according to their severity which is defined in terms of widths of cracks

The Structural cracks in pavement can be classified according to their severity, usually determined by the width of the crack. It is important to classify structural cracks by their severity as it can help determine the appropriate

repair technique. There are generally three types of structural cracks based on their width:

Hairline crack: This is the smallest type of structural crack and is usually less than 0.1mm wide. Hairline cracks are often difficult to detect and may not require immediate repair.

Medium crack: This crack is larger than the hairline crack and is usually 0.1 to 5 mm wide. Medium cracks can be repaired with crack sealing techniques, which involves filling the cracks with a sealant.

Major Crack: This is the most severe type of structural crack and is usually more than 5 mm wide. Large cracks can be repaired with patching techniques, which include removing damaged pavement and replacing it with new material.

In addition to the width of the crack, other factors such as the location and shape of the crack can also provide important information about the severity of the damage. For example, cracks that appear in a particular pattern, such as diagonal or parallel patterns, can indicate fundamental problems with pavement design or construction.

In general, classifying structural cracks according to their severity is an important part of pavement assessment and maintenance. By identifying and repairing structural cracks in a timely manner, pavement owners can prevent further damage and ensure the pavement's long-term performance and safety.

Failure Types of Cracks

Alligator Cracking.

Longitudinal (Linear) Cracking.

Transverse Cracking.

Edge Cracks.

Joint Reflection Cracks.

Slippage Cracks.

Pot Holes.

Depressions (bird baths) (Suryakanta, 2015)

Types of Defats Flexible Pavement

The Soft pavements, often composed of asphalt and aggregates, can develop a variety of defects

over time due to factors such as traffic loads, weather conditions, and aging. Some common types of defects in soft pavement include:

- **Marks:** These longitudinal indentations can form in the wheel tracks of the pavement due to traffic loads. Wheel ruts can lead to reduced drainage and roughness, and can affect the ride quality of the road surface.

- **Cracks:** Cracks can form in pavements due to many factors including temperature changes, aging and traffic loads. Different types of cracks include transverse cracks, longitudinal cracks and alligator cracks.

- **Bleeding:** This is excess asphalt binder that can build up on pavement surfaces, causing the surface to be slick, slippery. Excess asphalt binder, high temperatures or improper compaction can cause bleeding during construction.

- **Thrust:** This occurs when the pavement surface deforms under heavy traffic loads, causing a series of ridges and bumps to form. Rushing can lead to poor ride quality and reduced skid resistance.

- **Deformation:** The permanent deformation or deformation of the pavement due to traffic loads. Deformation can lead to reduced ride quality and poor drainage.

- **Potholes:** Potholes are holes or depressions in the pavement surface that can be caused by a variety of factors, including water infiltration, temperature changes, and traffic loading.

It is important to identify and repair these types of defects in a timely manner in order to maintain the performance and safety of the pavement. Regular maintenance and inspection can help identify defects early on and prevent further damage to the pavement (Ellsi, Langdale, & Cook, 2002).

Defects in flexible pavements can be repaired using a variety of techniques, depending on the type and severity of the defect. Some common repair techniques include:

- **Crack Sealing:** This involves filling cracks in the pavement with a sealant, which helps prevent moisture penetration and further

damage to the pavement. Crack sealing is commonly used for medium-sized cracks.

- Patch: This involves removing damaged pavement and replacing it with new material. Patching is commonly used for large cracks, potholes and other types of damage.
- Milling and resurfacing: This involves removing the top layer of the pavement and replacing it with a new layer of asphalt. This technique is often used for severe damage or when the road surface becomes rough and uneven.
- Overlay: This involves spreading a new layer of asphalt over the surface of the existing pavement. Coatings can be used to improve the ride quality of the pavement and prolong the life of the pavement (Ellsi, Langdale, & Cook, 2002).
- Reconstruction: This involves the complete replacement of the pavement structure, including the subfloor and the foundation. Reconstruction is often used for major damage or when the pavement has reached the end of its life.

It is important to select the right repair technique based on the type and severity of the defect, as well as the condition of the road surface and the amount of traffic. Regular maintenance and inspection can help identify faults early and prevent further pavement damage, reducing the need for costly long-term repairs.

Causes in Asphalt Various Causes of Crack Flexible Pavement

There are several reasons why cracks can develop on soft pavement, including:

- Thermal cracking: This is the most common type of pavement crack and is caused by temperature fluctuations. When the pavement is exposed to high temperatures, it expands, and when the temperature drops, it contracts. Over time, this repetitive expansion and contraction can cause pavement to crack.
- Fatigue cracking: This type of cracking is caused by the pavement being repeatedly loaded and unloaded, for example by heavy vehicles. Over time, repeated stress can cause pavement to crack.

- Reflective Cracking: Occurs when cracks in the lower layer of the pavement reflect through the surface layer, usually due to inadequate drainage or weak subfloor.
- Mass cracking: This occurs because the pavement shrinks and expands due to temperature fluctuations, resulting in interconnected cracks that look like a block.
- Slip Cracking: Occurs when the surface layer of the pavement moves or slides over the layers below, usually due to insufficient bonding between layers.
- Wheel line subsidence: The phenomenon of road surface deformation or subsidence due to repeated traffic loads on the same wheel arch.
- Moisture Damage: It is caused by water entering the pavement structure, weakening the pavement and possibly causing cracking.
- Construction issues: Poor construction practices, such as improper compaction, poor mix design, or poor drainage can also contribute to pavement cracking.

The Understanding what causes cracks is important in determining the most effective repair strategy to ensure pavement life and function (Wang, Mahboub, & Hancher, 2005).

There Are Various Causes of In Flexible Pavement

As mentioned earlier, there are several causes of cracks in soft pavement. Some of the more common causes include:

In Inappropriate pavement design: Inappropriate pavement design, including improper thickness, poor mix design, or inadequate drainage, can lead to premature cracking.

The Poor Construction Practices: Poor construction practices, such as improper compaction, poor mix design, or poor drainage, can also contribute to pavement cracking.

Environmental factors: Factors such as extreme heat, rainfall, and freeze-thaw cycles can all contribute to the development of pavement cracks.

Heavy traffic loads: Repetitive loads from heavy vehicles can cause fatigue cracks, marks, and other forms of pavement damage.

Aging: Over time, pavement becomes brittle and prone to cracking due to the natural aging process.

Improper maintenance: Lack of maintenance, such as lack of waterproofing or sealing of cracks, can lead to pavement deterioration and the development of cracks.

It is important to identify the underlying cause of pavement cracking in order to determine the most effective repair strategy and to ensure pavement life and function (Vishwakarma, & Patel, 2020).

Fatigue Cracking

Fatigue cracking is a common form of pavement deterioration caused by repetitive loading and unloading on the pavement surface, usually by heavy vehicles. Repeated stress on the pavement surface eventually leads to the formation of micro cracks that spread and link together, resulting in a network of interconnected cracks.

Fatigue cracking is typically characterized by multiple evenly spaced cracks, often appearing in a horizontal or diagonal pattern on the pavement surface. These cracks may start out as hairline cracks, but can eventually grow and deepen if left untreated, leading to loss of pavement strength and eventual pavement damage (Liang, & Sun, 2012; Kheradmandi, & Mehranfar, 2022).

Remedy:

There are a number of remedies for fatigue cracks in pavement, including:

- Crack Filling: This involves filling the cracks with a hot or cold sealant to prevent vapor penetration, moisture and other damage to the road surface.
- Crack Filler: Similar to Crack Sealer, but uses low viscosity material to fill cracks. It is often used for narrower cracks.
- Overlay: A new layer of asphalt is laid over an existing pavement to reinforce the pavement's texture and restore its load-carrying capacity.

Figure 30. Asphalt Damage
Source: Aziz, & Maniruzzaman, 2016

- Reconstruction: In the event of severe pavement damage, reconstruction may be required. This involves removing damaged pavement and rebuilding the pavement structure from scratch.
- Milling and resurfacing: This involves removing the top layer of the pavement surface and spreading a new layer of asphalt on top. This can be an effective way to restore ride quality on the pavement and solve crack problems.

It is necessary to base on the severity of fatigue cracks and the condition of the pavement to choose the appropriate treatment. Regular maintenance and preventive measures such as sealing cracks and prompt repair can help prevent or minimize the appearance of fatigue cracks in pavement.

Block Cracking

Mass cracking is a type of pavement deterioration that occurs as interconnected rectangular cracks in asphalt pavement. These cracks are usually formed in a pattern that looks

like a block or checkerboard, hence the name "cubic cracks".

Mass cracking is caused by many factors, including pavement aging, repeated traffic loads, temperature changes, and moisture ingress. As pavement ages, it becomes more brittle and prone to cracking. Repeated traffic loads cause stress on the pavement, which can lead to the formation of cracks in the blocks. The change in temperature causes the pavement to expand and contract, which can also lead to the formation of cracks in the blocks. Ingress of moisture weakens the pavement and can cause cracking.

Mass cracking can be a serious problem if left untreated, as it can lead to wider cracks and eventual failure. road surface. Therefore, it is

important to repair the cracks of the blocks as soon as possible to prevent further damage (Aziz, & Maniruzzaman, 2016).

The bulk crack treatment typically involves sealing the crack, filling the crack, or resurfacing it with a coating. Sealing and filling cracks helps prevent moisture from entering the pavement surface and causing further damage. Asphalt resurfacing involves applying a new layer of asphalt to the existing pavement to strengthen the pavement structure and restore its load-carrying capacity. In severe cases, rebuilding may be necessary to restore the structural integrity of the pavement (Kheradmandi, & Mehranfar, 2022).

Figure 31. Block Cracking
Source: Czerwinski, et al., 1999

Remedy:

Here are some bulk crack remedies:

- **Filling and Cracking:** These techniques involve filling the cracks with a hot or cold sealant to prevent moisture from entering and damage. different from the pavement block surface. Crack filling is generally used for wider cracks, while crack filling is used for narrower cracks.
- **Surface Resurfacing:** In cases of severe pavement damage, surface resurfacing can be an effective remedy. This involves spreading a new layer of asphalt over the existing pavement to strengthen the pavement's structure and restore its load-carrying capacity.

- **Reconstruction:** In the event of severe pavement damage, reconstruction may be required. This involves removing damaged pavement and rebuilding the pavement structure from scratch.

It is necessary to base on the severity of the block crack and the condition of the road surface to choose the appropriate treatment. Regular maintenance and preventive measures such as sealing cracks and prompt repairs can help prevent or minimize the appearance of cracks in pavement blocks (Kheradmandi, & Mehranfar, 2022).

Longitudinal Cracking

The longitudinal cracking is a common form of pavement deterioration that occurs as cracks parallel to the pavement axis. Cracks can occur in one or both wheel tracks and can be caused by a number of factors including aging, traffic loads and environmental conditions. If left untreated, longitudinal cracks can lead to more pavement damage, resulting in safety hazards and reduced ride quality.

The following are some remedies for longitudinal cracking:

- **Filling and Cracking:** These techniques involve filling cracks with a hot or cold sealant to prevent moisture from entering and causing further damage to the pavement surface. Crack filling is generally used for wider cracks, while crack filling is used for narrower cracks.
- **Milling and Resurfacing:** In cases of severe pavement damage, milling and resurfacing can be a viable solution. This involves removing the damaged pavement layer and spreading a new layer of asphalt over the existing pavement.
- **Filling:** In case of localized longitudinal cracks, leveling compounds can be used to overcome. This involves removing the damaged area and replacing it with new asphalt.

Reconstruction: In the event of severe pavement damage, reconstruction may be required. This involves removing damaged pavement and rebuilding the pavement structure from scratch.

It is necessary to base on the severity of longitudinal cracks and the condition of the road surface to choose appropriate remedial measures. Regular maintenance and preventive measures such as sealing cracks and prompt repair can help prevent or minimize the appearance of longitudinal cracks in the pavement (Feng, et al., 2020).

Figure 32. Longitudinal Cracking

Source: Czerwinski, et al., 1999

Transverse Cracking

In Longitudinal cracking is a common form of pavement deterioration that occurs as cracks parallel to the pavement axis. Cracks can occur in one or both wheel tracks and can be caused by a number of factors including aging, traffic loads and environmental conditions. If left untreated, longitudinal cracks can lead to more pavement damage, resulting in safety hazards and reduced ride quality (Hoang, & Nguyen, 2018).

Edge Cracking

The Edge cracking is a common problem in asphalt pavement, where longitudinal cracks form near the pavement edge due to a

combination of factors such as lack of support, high traffic loads, and temperature changes. Here are some possible remedies for chafing:

- **In Tackling the underlying problem:** Cracking can be a symptom of a more fundamental problem, such as poor drainage, foundation, etc. The foundation is not supportive enough or the pavement thickness is not enough. Fixing these problems can help prevent edge cracking.

- **Improved edge resistance:** The pavement edges are more prone to cracking in the middle due to less support. Therefore, enhancing curb support with measures such as pavement paving, road widening, or installing curbside drains can help reduce the risk of curb cracking.

- **Use the right blend design:** Using the right blend design taking into account specific weather and traffic conditions can help prevent edge cracking. Mixture design may include factors such as aggregate size, asphalt content, and the use of modifiers to improve performance.

- **Apply Sealant:** Applying sealant to edge cracks can help prevent water seepage, which can aggravate the crack.

- **Routine maintenance:** Regular maintenance, such as sealing cracks, can help prevent edge cracks from getting worse and spreading (Czerwinski, et al., 1999).

Remedy:

The fix the underlying problem: Edge cracking can be a symptom of a more fundamental problem, such as poor drainage, insufficient foundation support, or insufficient pavement thickness. Fixing these problems can help prevent edge cracking.

- **Improved edge resistance:** The pavement edges are more prone to cracking in the middle due to less support. Therefore, enhancing curb support with measures such as pavement paving, road widening, or installing curbside drains can help reduce the risk of curb cracking.

Figure 33. Edge Cracking
Source: Sreedhar, et al., 2021

- **Use the right blend design:** Using the right blend design taking into account specific weather and traffic conditions can help prevent edge cracking. Mixture design may include factors such as aggregate size, asphalt content, and the use of modifiers to improve performance.

Apply sealant: Applying sealant to edge cracks can help prevent water seepage, which can aggravate the crack

- **Routine maintenance:** Regular maintenance, such as sealing cracks, can help prevent edge cracks from getting worse and spreading (Choi, & Won, 2011).

Slippage Cracks

The Sliding cracking is a type of asphalt pavement failure that occurs when the asphalt pavement layer slips or slides over the underlying layer. This can occur due to lack of bonding between asphalt layers, heavy traffic loads or poor surface drainage. Here are some slip crack remedies:

- **Resurfacing:** In severe cases, when the asphalt layer has slipped or separated from the underlying layer, it may be necessary to redo the entire surface. road.
- **Removal of Affected Area:** For localized slippage, removal of the affected area and replacement with fresh asphalt can be an effective remedy.
- **Improve surface drainage:** Water can penetrate the pavement surface causing loss of adhesion between layers. Therefore, improving surface drainage through measures such as installing drainage pipes or improving pavement can help prevent slip cracks (Radhakrishnan, 2009).
- **Using an adhesive layer:** Coating a binder, which is a thin layer of asphalt emulsion, between existing and new asphalt layers can help improve interlayer adhesion.
- **Improve pavement design:** The pavement design can be improved by increasing the asphalt layer thickness, using a higher quality asphalt mix, or using geosynthetic materials to reinforce the asphalt layer road surface.

Figure 34. Slippage Cracks
Source: Sreedhar, et al., 2021

Remedy:

- **Resurfacing:** In severe cases, when the asphalt layer slips or separates from the layer below, it may be necessary to redo the entire pavement.
- **On removal of Affected Area:** For localized slippage, removal of the affected area and replacement with fresh asphalt can be an effective remedy.
- **Improve surface drainage:** Water can penetrate the pavement surface causing loss of adhesion between layers. Therefore, improving surface drainage through measures such as

installing drain pipes or improving pavement can help prevent slip cracks (Dheyaaldin, 2020).

- **Using an adhesive layer:** Using a binder, which is a thin layer of asphalt emulsion, between existing and new asphalt layers can help improve interlayer adhesion.
- **Improve pavement design:** The pavement design can be improved by increasing the asphalt layer thickness, using a higher quality asphalt mix, or using geosynthetic materials to reinforce the asphalt layer road surface.

Depressions Pavement

Missing, also known as rut, is a type of asphalt pavement crack that occurs when the road surface becomes uneven, with depressions or low points where water can collect. Subsidence can be caused by factors such as poor drainage, insufficient compaction during construction or high traffic loads. Here are some possible remedies for depressions:

- **Milling:** Milling is the process of removing part of a road surface to improve its level. This can be a cost-effective solution for local indentations.
- **Overlay:** In the case of wider depressions, pavement may be applied. This involves spreading a new layer of asphalt over the existing pavement to restore the flatness of the surface.
- **Patching:** Patching is a local repair method in which the indented area is removed and replaced with new asphalt.
- **Fix drainage problems:** If poor drainage is the cause of subsidence, correct drainage problems, such as adding or changing drainage structures, which can help prevent future subsidence.
- **Improvement of pavement texture:** If indentations are caused by unsuitable pavement construction, reinforcing pavement with geosynthetic materials or increasing pavement thickness can help prevent these marks. concave in the future.

Figure 35. Depressions Pavement
Source: NBT, n.d

Remedy:

Milling: Milling is a process in which part of the road surface is removed to improve its level. This can be a cost-effective solution for local indentations.

- **Overlay:** In the case of wider depressions, pavement may be applied. This involves spreading a new layer of asphalt over the existing pavement to restore the flatness of the surface.
- **Patching:** Patching is a local repair method in which the indented area is removed and replaced with new asphalt.
- **Fix drainage problems:** If poor drainage is the cause of subsidence, correct drainage problems, such as adding or changing drainage structures, which can help prevent future subsidence.
- **Improve pavement structure:** If pavement indentation is not suitable, reinforcing pavement with geosynthetic materials or increasing pavement thickness can help prevent future dents.

Rutting Pavement

Wheel ruts are a type of asphalt pavement deterioration that occurs when the surface of the road is worn away and forms dents or longitudinal marks. Wheel ruts can be caused by a number of factors, including high traffic loads, poor drainage, and improper pavement design. Here are some remedies for rutting:

- **Milling:** Milling is the process of removing part of a road surface to improve its

flatness. This can be a cost-effective solution for localized wheel ruts.

- **Overlay:** In case of more subsidence, pavement coating can be applied. This involves spreading a new layer of asphalt over the existing pavement to restore the flatness of the surface.
- **Stabilization:** Stabilization is a process in which a chemical stabilizer or reinforcing material is added to the asphalt mixture to improve its strength and resistance to rutting.
- **Improve drainage:** Improving pavement drainage can help prevent rutting by reducing the amount of water seeping into the pavement and improving the pavement's bearing capacity (Cubero-Fernandez, et al., 2017).

Figure 36. Rutting Pavement
Source: Mazurowski, 2021

Corrugation

A corrugation, also known as a washboard or ripple, is a type of asphalt pavement crack that occurs when the pavement surface becomes undulating or wavy, with a series of ledges and grooves perpendicular to the direction of traffic. Ripples can be caused by a number of factors, including poor compression during construction, high traffic loads, and improper pavement design. Here are some possible remedies for ripples:

- **Milling:** Milling is the process of removing part of a road surface to improve its flatness. This can be a cost-effective solution for local folds. This involves spreading a new layer of asphalt over the existing pavement to restore the flatness of the surface.
- **Stabilization:** Stabilization is a process in which a chemical stabilizer or reinforcing

material is added to an asphalt mixture to improve its strength and resistance to creasing.

Figure 37. Corrugation
Source: Mazurowski, 2021

Shoving Pavement

Rubble is a form of asphalt pavement breakdown that occurs when the road surface deforms and shifts under the action of traffic loads, resulting in a series of ridges and ripples in the pavement surface. Rubbing can be caused by a number of factors, including high traffic, high tire pressure and improper pavement design. Here are some possible remedies for the hustle

- **Milling:** Milling is the process of removing part of the pavement to improve its level. This can be a cost-effective solution to local scrambles.
- **Overlay:** In case of more jostling, road coating can be applied. This involves spreading a new layer of asphalt over the existing pavement to restore the flatness of the surface (Rodica, Boitor, & Mihai Liviu, 2022).
- **Stabilization:** Stabilization is a process in which a chemical stabilizer or reinforcing material is added to the asphalt mixture to improve its strength and resistance to jostling.
- **Improve compaction:** Improving the compaction of asphalt during construction can help prevent future crushing.

Figure 38. Shoving Pavement
Source: Kulkarni, 2022

Stitching Pavement

The chipping is a pavement repair technique used to repair longitudinal cracks in concrete pavement. This technique involves drilling holes on each side of the crack and then placing steel dowels in the holes. These studs act as conveying devices and help prevent the crack from expanding and spreading further. Here are the general steps to stitch pavement.

- **Saw cutting:** The first step is to saw the pavement on each side of the crack to create a clean, straight edge. This will help ensure the crack is properly aligned for the stitching process.
- **Drilling:** Next, holes are drilled into the pavement on either side of the crack. Holes shall form a perpendicular angle to the crack and be spaced in accordance with pavement design specifications.
- **Setting the pin:** The steel pin is then placed in the hole. The studs must be long enough to cross the width of the pavement and must be coated with an adhesive to help them adhere to the pavement.
- **Mortar:** A high strength grout is then poured into the holes around the pin to provide additional support and adhesion.
- **Sealing:** Finally, the crack is sealed with a suitable sealant to prevent moisture from entering the crack and causing further damage.

It is important to note that the specific steps and materials used to sew the pavement can vary depending on the design and condition of the pavement, so it is best to consult of a qualified

engineer or contractor for specific recommendations Rodica, Boitor, & Mihai Liviu, 2022).

In Cross Stitching Pavement

Cross stitch is a pavement repair technique used to repair horizontal cracks in concrete pavement. This technique involves drilling holes through the crack and then placing steel rods or wire through the holes diagonally, much like a cross stitch.

Figure 39. In Cross Stitching Pavement
Source: Kulkarni, 2022

Slot Stitching Pavement

In Joint stitching is a pavement repair technique used to repair horizontal cracks in concrete

pavement. This technique involves sawing a slot or groove through the crack, inserting a steel plate or dowel into the slot, and filling the gap with mortar or high strength epoxy material (Pavement Interactive, n.d.1)

Figure 40. Lot Stitching Pavement
Source: The Constructor, n.d.

U-bar Stitching

Is a pavement repair technique used to repair longitudinal or transverse cracks in concrete pavement. This technique involves drilling U-shaped holes through the crack and inserting U-shaped steel rods into the holes. U-shaped bars are then anchored to the pavement on either side of the crack with high strength mortar or epoxy material.

Figure 41. U-Bar Stitching
Source: IGGA, 2010

Prime Coat

The Primer is a small emulsion of bitumen or bitumen that is applied to the absorbent surface prior to the application of the asphalt coating.

Primer is used to prepare the surface for subsequent asphalt coatings by forming a bond between the surface and the asphalt, reducing the absorption of bitumen into the surface and preventing the surface from becoming too dry.

Figure 42. Prime Coat

Source: PetroNaft, 2023

Finishing Coat

The top coat is the final layer of material applied to the surface to provide a smooth, uniform and aesthetically pleasing appearance. The final coating can be applied to a variety of surfaces, including walls, ceilings, floors and even roads (Vishwakarma, & Patel, 2020)

Permeability for Pavements

On Pavement permeability testing is an important process that helps determine how easily water can penetrate and flow through pavement layers. This is important because excessive water infiltration can damage the pavement structure, reduce its service life and cause safety problems.

There are several methods used to test pavement permeability, including:

Constant Head Permeability Test: This involves placing a pavement sample in a permeability meter and pouring amount of water of constant head on one side of the sample. The water flow through the sample is then measured and the permeability coefficient calculated.

Falling Head Permeability Test: This method is similar to the constant head test, but the head decreases over time when measuring the flow of water through the sample. Then, the permeability coefficient is calculated based on the change of water column and flow rate (Chen, et al., 2020).

Presser test: This involves placing a small portion of pavement on the presser plate and applying a known pressure to the surface. The water flow through the pavement is then measured and the permeability coefficient calculated.

The Permeability testing can help determine the effectiveness of pavement drainage systems and can be used to optimize pavement design and maintenance strategies (Chen, et al., 2020).

Important

The Permeability is very important for pavement because it directly affects the pavement's ability to drain and resist damage from water ingress. If water seeps through the pavement layers, it can weaken the foundation, reduce the bearing capacity of the pavement, leading to the formation of potholes and cracks.

The ater penetration tests are therefore essential to assess the quality of pavement materials and ensure that they meet the required specifications for drainage systems. This information can be used to design pavements that are more durable, resistant to water damage and have a longer life.

In addition, water permeability is also important to maintain safe driving conditions. If water accumulates on the road surface due to poor permeability, it can reduce tire grip and increase the risk of water skidding, which can lead to an accident.

In general, permeability plays an important role in pavement performance and life and must be considered when designing, constructing and maintaining pavements.

Permeability Test to Help Solution in Pavement

Permeability testing can help find solutions to pavement seepage problems. By conducting permeability tests, the permeability coefficient of pavement materials can be determined and suitable solutions can be developed to solve any seepage related problem. Here are some ways permeability testing can help find a solution:

Selecting the right pavement material: Permeability testing can help determine the permeability coefficient of different pavement materials. Based on this information, the right material with the right permeability can be selected to ensure that the pavement can drain efficiently and resist water-related damage.

Designing Efficient Drainage Systems: Permeation tests can help determine the drainage capacity of a pavement. Based on this information, appropriate drainage systems can be designed and integrated into the pavement structure to facilitate efficient drainage and

minimize water-related damage (Ali, Al-Khafaji, & Abbood, 2022).

Optimizing pavement maintenance: Permeation testing can be used to monitor the condition of the pavement over time and identify any seepage-related problems that may arise. By identifying these problems early, appropriate maintenance and repair strategies can be implemented to prevent further damage and ensure the longevity of the pavement.

In general, permeability testing is an important tool for developing solutions to pavement permeability problems. By determining the permeability coefficient of the pavement material and assessing the pavement's drainage capacity, it is possible to select the right material and drainage system to optimize pavement performance and minimize damage. water related.

For the drop height test arrangement, the test piece shall be connected from the top inlet to the chosen riser. The bottom outlet shall be open and the time it takes for the water level to drop from the known initial height to the known final height, measured above the center of the outlet, shall be recorded. The riser shall be filled with water and the test repeated until three consecutive observations of approximately the same duration; time periods are recorded for the collapse of the top.

From the same initial values to the final values, as in the first determination. In addition, after selecting the initial and final pitch h_1 and h_2 , respectively, it is important to note the time periods such that the pitch decreases from h_1 to $\sqrt{h_1 h_2}$ and similarly from $\sqrt{h_1 h_2}$ to h_2 . The time interval must be the same; otherwise, the observation must be repeated after the riser is filled.

$$\text{Permeability Falling Head (K)} = 2.303 \times \frac{a(L)}{A(t_f - t_i)} \times \log_{10} \left(\frac{h_1}{h_2} \right) \quad (13)$$

Where,

- a is Area of Tube
- A is Area of Soil Specimen
- L is Length of Soil specimen
- $t_f - t_i$ is Time Interval (T)
- h_1 is Initial Head
- h_2 is Final Head

Figure 43. Permeability Test

Source: Civil Engineering calculators.com, n.d.

Conclusion

The study explores the use of artificial intelligence (AI) for detecting and repairing pavement cracks. Traditional methods for pavement inspection and maintenance are labor-intensive, costly, and often inaccurate. The implementation of AI, specifically deep learning algorithms, offers a more efficient and precise approach. These algorithms can analyze high-resolution images of road surfaces, accurately detecting and classifying various types of cracks such as longitudinal, transverse, block, and crocodile cracks. Additionally, the AI system can assess the severity of these cracks and recommend appropriate repair solutions, enhancing the overall effectiveness and cost-efficiency of pavement maintenance. This innovative approach aims to improve road safety, reduce maintenance costs, and ensure the sustainability of pavements.

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